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Application of nitrified urine fertilizer and fecal compost for growing kohlrabi in a controlled greenhouse environment

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Closing the nutrient loop between food consumption and crop production is essential for keeping nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) flows within safe planetary boundaries. Separately collecting and treating sanitary streams to produce human excreta-derived fertilizers (HEDF), such as nitrified urine fertilizer (NUF) and fecal compost (FC), could partly replace fossil-based mineral fertilizers while reducing nutrient pollution from N and P discharges to aquatic systems. However, broader HEDF adoption is constrained by limited knowledge of crop-specific performance and the fate of potential contaminants. This study evaluated the combined use of NUF from source-separated urine and FC from dry toilet contents for greenhouse cultivation of kohlrabi (*Brassica oleracea* var. *gongylodes* L.) in comparison with a synthetic multi-nutrient mineral fertilizer. In addition to crop performance, plant N uptake, soil N dynamics, and the fate of doxycycline as an indicator pharmaceutical were assessed to provide an integrated evaluation of agronomic and environmental implications. HEDF and mineral fertilizer treatments produced comparable yields, with no significant differences in leaf, bulb, or root biomass. However, total plant N uptake was 13% higher under HEDF fertilization, driven by increased N contents in leaves (+30%), bulbs (+29%), and roots (+13%). At harvest, soil mineral N concentrations were on average five times higher in the mineral fertilizer treatment than in the HEDF treatment, whereas soil organic N concentrations showed an opposite trend and were approximately 25% lower under mineral fertilization. Doxycycline, detected in the applied FC, remained below the limit of quantitation in both kohlrabi bulbs and soil at harvest. These findings indicate that the combined application of NUF and FC can effectively substitute mineral fertilizer in kohlrabi cultivation. The results further suggest that HEDF application may modify short-term soil N cycling by increasing N immobilization and reducing soil mineral N accumulation compared with mineral fertilization. Long-term studies are needed to evaluate the effects of repeated FC application on soil organic carbon, N leaching, and potential contaminant uptake by crops.

KEYWORDS

bio-based circular economy, micropollutants, nutrient recycling, plant nutrition, resource-oriented sanitation, soil nitrogen, zero pollution

1 Introduction

Human activities have exceeded safe planetary boundaries for nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) flows, largely due to intensive fertilizer use in agriculture (Rockström et al., 2009; Sutton et al., 2011; Steffen et al., 2015). While synthetic fertilizers have greatly increased food production, their excessive use contributes to eutrophication, biodiversity

loss, water contamination, and greenhouse gas emissions (Mihelcic et al., 2011; Chowdhury et al., 2014; Garnier et al., 2015). These challenges have increased interest in circular nutrient management strategies, including nutrient recovery from human excreta and organic waste streams (Simha and Ganesapillai, 2017; Harder et al., 2019).

Human excreta-derived fertilizers (HEDF), which include, among others, nitrified urine fertilizers (NUFs) and fecal compost (FC), present a dual opportunity: i) reducing the environmental footprint of sanitation systems, while ii) supplying agriculture with renewable sources of nutrients (Larsen et al., 2021; Starck et al., 2024). Their use supports Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those related to clean water, sustainable cities, responsible consumption, and climate action (Hoffmann et al., 2020; Larsen et al., 2021). Urine-based fertilizers have a high potential to provide agricultural crops with nutrients (Saliu et al., 2024) but were found to increase the sodium adsorption ratio of soils (Hansen et al., 2026). The combination of both NUF and FC is particularly interesting, as FC alone is not sufficient to provide crops with N (Schröder et al., 2021), and NUF has been found to be a highly efficient N fertilizer (Udert and Wächter, 2012; Fumasoli et al., 2016; Mauerer et al., 2023). Indeed, Sangare et al. (2015) found that the combination of FC and urine-based fertilizer gave a higher yield than each of the HEDF alone in a pot experiment with okra.

Although stored urine can be used directly as a fertilizer, stabilizing treatments like dehydration or nitrification are needed to mitigate ammonia emissions from fertilizer storage and application on agricultural soils (Maurer et al., 2006). Compost derived from fecal matter co-composted together with organic kitchen or garden waste contributes not only nutrients but also organic matter that improves soil structure, water retention, and microbial activity (Sangare et al., 2015; Schröder et al., 2021; Hansen et al., 2026). Thermophilic composting of fecal matter has been found to efficiently inactivate pathogens if elevated temperatures can be held for a certain time during the process (Vinneras, 2007; Niwagaba et al., 2009). However, limited knowledge is available about the suitability of HEDFs for different cultivars and production systems (Van den Broek et al., 2024), and in particular, how they perform in comparison to mineral synthetic fertilizers (Häfner et al., 2023), which are widely used in horticultural and agricultural food production. While previous studies have primarily focused on agronomic performance and yield comparisons between HEDF and mineral fertilizers (e.g., Häfner et al., 2023; Boness et al., 2024), less attention has been given to the combined assessment of crop performance, soil nitrogen dynamics, and pharmaceutical fate within the same experimental system. In particular, mechanistic insights into how combined NUF and FC applications influence soil mineral N dynamics and potential contaminant transfer under controlled horticultural production conditions remain limited.

In addition, challenges remain regarding the safety, social acceptance, and chemical purity of these materials (Brochier et al., 2012; Krause et al., 2021; Joveniaux et al., 2022). One key concern is the presence of residual pharmaceuticals, including antibiotics, hormones, and analgesics, which may persist through treatment processes and enter the food chain *via* plant uptake (Winker, 2009; Helmecke et al., 2020; Köpping et al., 2020). Although processes such as alkaline dehydration, composting, and activated carbon filtration have shown promising results in

reducing pharmaceutical loads in HEDF (Özel Duygan et al., 2021; Senecal et al., 2022), the fate of these contaminants in agricultural applications, particularly in greenhouse systems, is still insufficiently understood. Controlled environments allow for precise management of variables such as irrigation and leaching but may also alter the dynamics of pharmaceutical sorption, degradation, and uptake (Esculier et al., 2019; Martin et al., 2023). Understanding these dynamics is essential for ensuring the safe use of recycled fertilizers in food production, especially in urban agriculture or closed-loop systems where local nutrient recycling is a key sustainability strategy.

To address the existing knowledge gaps and to investigate the suitability of HEDF for food production, in this study, the combined use of NUF and FC is compared against a conventional mineral synthetic fertilizer for the cultivation of kohlrabi (*Brassica oleracea* var. *gongylodes* L.) in a controlled greenhouse environment. Kohlrabi is a fast-growing, widely consumed brassica with significant relevance to both conventional and organic farming systems. It is also a good model crop for studying nutrient uptake and potential contaminant transfer due to its bulbous stem and relatively short growth cycle (Martin et al., 2023; Mauerer et al., 2023). Furthermore, as a short-cycle vegetable crop intended for direct human consumption, kohlrabi represents a relevant model for assessing both fertilizer efficiency and food safety aspects associated with HEDF application in intensive horticultural systems. The main objective of this study is to evaluate how the different fertilization treatments—HEDF and mineral fertilizer—influence plant growth, nutrient uptake, and the potential accumulation of pharmaceutical residues in edible tissues. By analyzing nutrient dynamics in both soils and plant biomass, as well as tracing pharmaceutical compounds, the study aims to generate insights into the performance and safety of HEDF to provide further evidence of the benefits and risks associated with their use in food crop production.

It is hypothesized that: i) the HEDF treatment will result in comparable kohlrabi yields due to the nutrient-rich composition of NUF and positive effects on soil structure and fertility from FC; ii) through the use of FC in the HEDF treatment, N dynamics in soil will be altered due to the increased organic matter supply potentially improving nutrient retention in soil and reducing soil mineral N (N_{min}) content; and iii) pharmaceutical residues originating from FC will largely remain in the soil, where they are subject to microbial degradation or immobilization, thereby limiting their transfer to plant tissues and ensuring the safety of the edible product.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Experimental set-up

2.1.1 General set-up

A greenhouse plot experiment with red kohlrabi (*Brassica oleracea* var. *gongylodes* L.) was conducted between February and May 2024 at the Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops (IGZ) in Großbeeren, Germany (52°22'N, 13°18'E, alt. 40 m) (Supplementary Figure S1). The greenhouse used includes 9 soil plots that are separated by concrete walls and are closed at the

bottom to allow for leachate collection through a drainage tube at the lowest position. Each plot has a surface area of 1.8×8 m and a soil depth of 0.8–0.9 m. The concrete bottom is built with a slope of 2% from each long side to the center with the drainage tube and a slope of 0.5% over its entire length. The greenhouse was constructed in 1999 and filled with local soil, which is classified as lightly loamy sand and has a bulk density of 1.6 g cm^{-3} . The soil was homogenized by mixing before filling the plots to minimize the baseline variability between plots. The greenhouse setup allows for heating, shading, and automated irrigation. Heating pipes are also laid in the soil in two stacked rows at a depth of 70 cm and 80 cm to prevent freezing of the soil in winter.

For this study, a systematic strip design was used, in which the plots were fertilized in an alternating sequence with mineral fertilizer (plots 2, 4, 6, and 8) and HEDF (plots 3, 5, 7, 9). This design was used to account for spatial microclimate gradients within the greenhouse, in particular different light intensities at the edges and in the middle of the greenhouse due to the wall and roof constructions, to ensure that each treatment is equally represented across these gradients. Furthermore, because all plots were filled with the same homogenized soil, it was assumed that soil conditions were largely consistent between plots. Plot 1 was left unfertilized to have a balanced number of replicates for the mineral fertilizer and HEDF treatments (each with $n = 4$), and was used as an illustrative example of the effect of fertilizer on visitor groups. A schematic overview of the design, together with a picture from the greenhouse, can be found in [Supplementary Figure S1](#). In each plot, a total of 130 seedlings of red kohlrabi (*Brassica oleracea* var. *gongyloides* L.) were planted on 20 March 2024 in five rows per plot. The distance between plants was 25 cm within the rows and 30 cm between the rows, yielding a plant density of $13.3 \text{ plants m}^{-2}$ on the usable area of the plots (9.75 m^2). Larger spaces of 40 cm were left at the edges of each plot to minimize the effects of the separating concrete walls on plant growth and about 1 m lengthwise of the plots was occupied by the irrigation system (see [Supplementary Figure S1](#)). Between each kohlrabi row, a drip hose was placed (four per plot) to allow for automated irrigation during the cultivation period.

2.1.2 Pre-trials in the greenhouse

Prior to the experiment described in this study, two pre-trials took place. The first pre-trial was done with a mixture of different salad and kohlrabi cultivars from May to July 2023 in order to identify the most suitable cultivar for the specific growing conditions in the greenhouse. No fertilization was done during this pre-trial to establish homogeneous nutrient contents in the top soil layer, particularly for nitrogen (N). This was followed by a second pre-trial from the end of October 2023 to the beginning of February 2024, in which the fertilizer treatments were established, using similar fertilizer application rates as described for this study below (same application rate of fecal compost, addition of Aurin and mineral fertilizer to meet plant N demand adjusted for soil mineral N content). However, due to low solar radiation amounts during that period, the kohlrabi growth was low, and the bulbs did not reach a marketable size. In addition, high amounts of irrigation were applied during that pre-trial to collect leachate from the bottom of the plots, which led to intense leaching of the mineral fertilizer applied that was visible in impaired plant growth. Therefore, the

TABLE 1 Composition of Aurin®, the nitrified urine fertilizer (NUF) used in the greenhouse trial according as specified by the manufacturer VUNA.

Type	Parameter	Value	Unit
General	Total organic carbon	0.1	%
Macronutrients	Total nitrogen (N)	4.2	%
	Ammonium-N	2.1	%
	Nitrate-N	2.1	%
	Total phosphate (P_2O_5)	0.4	%
	Potassium oxide (K_2O)	1.8	%
	Sulphur trioxide (SO_3)	0.8	%
Micronutrients	Boron	0.0015	%
	Chloride	3.1	%
	Iron	0.0001	%
	Sodium	1.7	%
	Zinc	0.0012	%

results of the second pre-trial are not considered in this study, while the previous fertilization is taken into account for interpreting the results.

2.1.3 Growth conditions

Prior to planting the kohlrabi seedlings in the greenhouse soil, seeds were germinated in February and pre-cultivated under greenhouse conditions until the two-to three-leaf stage and transferred in pots to outside climate conditions for 2 weeks at the Beginning of March (hardening). This was followed by a 2-month growth period in the greenhouse. During the growth period, no additional plant protection measures were required, as the greenhouse set-up reduced the pressure from insect pests and fungal diseases. During the experiment, climate data were continuously monitored and recorded by a climate computer, with an average air temperature of 15°C and 58% relative humidity. The heating was set to $12/10^\circ\text{C}$ (day/night), and roof-top ventilation opened at temperatures $>15^\circ\text{C}$. Artificial lighting was applied from 6 a.m. to 12 p.m. CET if PAR levels were below $180 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Drip irrigation was done with tap water to maintain ~60% of the soil's maximum water holding capacity. Irrigation was conducted in three intervals per day, initially in 15-min intervals until 24 April 2024 ($\sim 10 \text{ L m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$) and subsequently in 45-min intervals ($\sim 30 \text{ L m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$).

2.2 Fertilizer treatments

2.2.1 Human excreta-derived fertilizers

Two HEDF were tested and used in the study ([Supplementary Figure S2](#)): 1) Aurin, which is a nitrified urine fertilizer (NUF) in liquid form, and 2) fecal compost derived from the solid contents of dry toilets (FC).

Aurin is already authorized as a fertilizer in Switzerland, Liechtenstein, Austria, and France ([Vuna GmbH, 2025](#)). It is produced *via* the VUNA process, which stands for “Valorization

TABLE 2 Composition of the fecal compost (FC) used in the greenhouse trial. Data from laboratory analysis was extracted from the dataset of Mühlenberg et al. (2025) for the compost batch 'MK7'.

Type	Parameter	Value	Unit
General	Dry matter content	55.7	% FM
	Organic matter	21.2	% DM
	Alkaline active ingredients	6.68	%CaO DM
	pH (aqueous extract)	9.1	-
	Salt content	0.23	%KCl DM
	Carbon content	14	% DM
	Macronutrients	Total nitrogen (N)	1.03
Ammonium-N		66	mg/kg FM
Nitrate-N		17	mg/kg FM
Total phosphate (P ₂ O ₅)		1.05	% DM
Soluble phosphate (P ₂ O ₅)		81	mg/kg FM
Potassium oxide (K ₂ O)		1.08	% DM
Calcium		3.64	% DM
Magnesium oxide (MgO)		1.02	% DM
Sulphur		0.18	% DM
Micronutrients	Cobalt	0.0011	% DM
	Copper	0.0029	% DM
	Iron	2	% DM
	Manganese	0.076	% DM
	Molybdenum	0.00052	% DM
	Nickel	0.0041	% DM
	Selenium	0.21	% DM
	Sodium	0.14	% DM
	Zinc	0.014	% DM

FM, fresh matter; DM, dry matter.

of Urine Nutrients in Africa" (Udert et al., 2016) and was developed by the Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag) and later commercialized by VUNA GmbH, based in Dübendorf, Switzerland. The Aurin used in this study was produced from stored urine collected by source-separating toilets (save! by LAUFEN Bathrooms AG, Laufen, Switzerland) installed at Eawag's main research facility. There, urine is collected in storage tanks in the building's basement and treated in a VUNA system. The treatment involves a three-step process (VunaNexus AG, 2026): i) urine undergoes biological nitrification to achieve an NH₄⁺/NO₃⁻ ratio of 1:1; ii) nitrified urine is filtered through activated carbon to eliminate trace contaminants such as pharmaceuticals and hormones; and iii) the liquid is concentrated through evaporation in a distiller, resulting in a volume reduction of 95%–97% and providing distilled water as a by-product. The composition of Aurin is shown in Table 1.

The FC used in this study originated from the recycling plant of Finizio GmbH in Eberswalde, Germany (Finizio GmbH, 2026). The

TABLE 3 Composition of the mineral fertilizer (Osmocote® Pro 3–4M) used in the greenhouse trial according as specified by the manufacturer ICL.

Type	Parameter	Value	Unit
Macronutrients	Total nitrogen (N)	19	%
	Ammonium-N	8.2	%
	Nitrate-N	6.3	%
	Carbamide-N	4.5	%
	Total phosphate (P ₂ O ₅)	9	%
	Water-soluble P ₂ O ₅	6.8	%
	Potassium oxide (K ₂ O)*	10	%
	Total magnesium oxide (MgO)	2	%
	Water-soluble MgO	1.3	%
	Sulphur trioxide (SO ₃)	0.8	%
Micronutrients	Boron*	0.01	%
	Total copper	0.037	%
	Water-soluble copper	0.023	%
	Total iron	0.3	%
	EDTA chelate iron	0.06	%
	Manganese	0.04	%
	Total molybdenum	0.015	%
	Water-soluble molybdenum	0.01	%
	Zinc	0.011	%

*Completely in water-soluble form.

recycling plant mainly processes dry toilet contents that are collected from mobile dry separating toilets stationed at various festivals in Germany. These toilets allow to collect solids (feces, toilet paper, straw-based litter) directly in bins of different sizes (30–240 L) that can be sealed with an air-tight lid for transportation (Krause et al., 2024). The bins are fitted with an outlet for liquids at the bottom that also allows the separate collection of percolated urine to avoid odor nuisance. Through the percolation of urine, the dry toilet contents are also enriched with nitrogen. On average, the dry toilet contents consist of approximately 50% human feces and 50% straw meal and toilet paper. After transport to the recycling plant in Eberswalde, dry toilet contents are first treated in a specialized hygienization container at temperatures >70 °C for 1 week, where the inactivation of pathogens is facilitated by aerobic microbial decomposition through additional straw inputs and active aeration. Following this, humification is done through controlled aerobic composting in windrows together with additives such as clay minerals, freshly mown grass, and municipal green waste to stabilize nutrients and provide further substrates for microbial activity. Oxygen supply during the 6–8 weeks composting phase is ensured by frequently mixing the material inside the windrows with a rotary turner, ensuring further hygienization of the material at temperatures of up to 65 °C. In a last step, the stabilized compost is sieved to remove non-compostable foreign materials such as wet wipes, hygiene products or packaging materials, yielding the final FC

product. The composition of the FC batch that was used in this study is shown in [Table 2](#). Additional information on contaminants (organic pollutants, pathogens, and heavy metals) can be found in [Supplementary Table S1](#).

2.2.2 Mineral fertilizer

A commercially available mineral compound fertilizer (Osmocote® Pro 3-4M, ICL Deutschland Vertriebs GmbH, Nordhorn, Germany) was used as a benchmark for comparing the performance of the two HEDF. The composition of the mineral fertilizer is shown in [Table 3](#). Osmocote® Pro 3-4M is a fully-coated slow-release fertilizer with a duration of effect of three to 4 months and a formulation with a high NPK content, designed to deliver optimal growing results for fast-growing plants.

2.2.3 Fertilizer application

Using the fertilizers described above, two different fertilizer treatments were implemented: i) HEDF—combining the use of FC and NUF; ii) Mineral fertilizer. The FC compost was applied according to typical compost practices (10 t of dry matter per hectare), while NUF and mineral fertilizer were added to match plant N demand. The N demand of the kohlrabi crop was estimated at 230 kg N ha⁻¹ (Feller et al., 2011), equivalent to 0.331 kg N per 14.4 m² plot. However, the actual fertilizer application rates were adjusted according to the German Fertiliser Ordinance (Klages and Schultheiß, 2020) by taking into account the soil mineral nitrogen (N_{min}) found in 0–30 cm depth (i.e., the main rooting horizon of kohlrabi) prior to cultivation and the N mineralization of previously applied FC in the HEDF treatment. In consequence, the actual amount of N applied varied between 208 and 226 kg N/ha for the eight fertilized plots ([Supplementary Table S2](#)). For fecal compost, it was assumed that 5% of total N from the current application was mineralized during the cultivation period, and another 4% of total N from the previous FC application in the preceding pre-trial following DüV guidelines. FC and mineral fertilizer were applied entirely in a single dose that was evenly distributed across the plot surface and incorporated manually into the top 10 cm of soil using a hand hoe 1 day before planting (2024-03-19). For NUF, the application was split into three equal doses to avoid potential salt stress due to the high sodium content in Aurin and to provide N to the crop when the demand is highest. Aurin was diluted by 1:10 with tap water and was distributed on the soil using watering cans. The first dose was evenly distributed over the total plot surface, while the second and third doses were applied close to the soil beneath the kohlrabi plants. The first NUF dose was given directly after FC application (2024-03-19), the second 3 weeks after planting (2024-04-15) to support leaf growth, and the third 5 weeks after planting (2024-04-30) to support bulb growth.

2.3 Harvesting, sampling, and analysis

2.3.1 Harvesting and plant sampling

The fully grown kohlrabi plants ([Figure 1](#)) were harvested 8 weeks after planting in greenhouse soil (2024-05-15). From each plot, 8 plants were selected as representative samples,

intentionally excluding any individuals showing signs of abnormal growth or visible damage. The selected plants were divided into edible bulbs, leaves, and roots, and each plant part was weighed to determine its fresh matter (FM). The plant components were then cut into pieces approximately 2 cm on each side, which were combined into mixed samples. From each plant compartment, three subsamples were processed as follows: One portion was dried at 60 °C to constant weight, then finely ground (<0.25 mm) for total nitrogen (N) analysis. A second portion was dried at 105 °C for the determination of dry matter (DM) content. The third subsample was frozen at -18 °C to prevent microbial and enzymatic activity and stored for potential pharmaceutical residue analysis. The remaining plants per plot were also harvested, counted, and included in the calculation of the total fresh biomass yield per plot.

2.3.2 Soil sampling

Soil samples were taken at two stages during the experiment: 1) before fertilization and planting (after the second pre-trial) on 2024-02-09, and 2) following plant harvest on 2024-05-15. From each plot, six soil cores were taken in a diagonal transect from the top 30 cm of the soil profile, then mixed into a composite sample. From this mix, four approximately 200 g subsamples were extracted: One subsample was dried at 60 °C, then stored for total nitrogen, carbon to nitrogen ratio (C/N), and soil organic carbon (C_{org}) measurements. The second and third subsamples were kept frozen at -18 °C to inhibit microbial activity and preserved for later analyses, i.e., mineral nitrogen (N_{min}) analysis and pharmaceutical residue analysis. The fourth sample was directly sent to an external laboratory (AGROLAB Agrarzentrum GmbH, Leinefelde, Germany) for measuring pH value and nutrient contents (phosphorus, P; potassium, K; magnesium, Mg; boron, B; copper, Cu; manganese, Mn; sodium, Na; zinc, Zn).

2.3.3 Fertilizer, soil, and plant analysis

To ensure the quality of FC before its application, comprehensive assessments were conducted based on the DIN SPEC 91421 guidelines on “Quality assurance of recycling products from dry toilets for use in horticulture” (DIN Deutsches Institut für Normierung e.V., 2020). Details on the analysis methods and results for the compost batch ‘MK7’ utilized in this study can be found in the dataset of Mühlenberg et al. (2025) that was gained as part of the REGION. innovativ-zirkulierBAR project (Krause et al., 2025). Briefly, the analysis included a wide range of parameters such as dry matter content, pH, organic matter content, macro- and micronutrients, heavy metals, microbial hygiene indicators (*Salmonella* spp., *E. coli*, *Enterococci*, *Clostridium perfringens*), dioxins and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), per-fluorinated tensides (PFTs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and a screening of 98 pharmaceutical substances ([Supplementary Table S3](#)). The latter was repeated again on an FC sample taken on 2024-02-21, as the utilized FC has been stored for several months after the first pharmaceutical screening took place directly after completion of the compost batch in October 2023. The pharmaceutical screening was done by an external laboratory (JenaBios GmbH, Jena, Germany). Aurin, being a certified product

FIGURE 1
 Pictures of the kohlrabi plants from two different perspectives, taken 1 day before the harvest (2024-05-14). The upper picture shows the unfertilized plot (P1) in front, while the picture below was taken from the opposite direction. Mineral fertilizer plots: P2, P4, P6, P8; Recycling fertilizer plots: P3, P5, P7, P9.

with highly efficient removal of pharmaceutical residues during the activated carbon filtration step (Köpping et al., 2020; Özel Duygan et al., 2021), was not analyzed, and compositional data were obtained from Vuna GmbH.

For C/N and soil Corg analyses, plant and soil samples were ground to a fine powder using a steel ball mill (MM400; RETSCH GmbH, Haan, Germany). Total C and total N concentrations were determined using an elemental analyzer (vario EL cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langensfeld, Germany) and used to calculate the C/N ratio. For the measurement of soil Corg, the system was modified with a combustion tube that was operated at 550 °C to release organically bound C only. For the determination of soil Nmin in the form of ammonium (NH₄⁺) and nitrate (NO₃⁻), frozen soil samples were sent to an external laboratory (AGROLAB Agrarzentrum GmbH, Leinefelde, Germany). Soil organic nitrogen

(Norg) was calculated as the difference between total soil N and Nmin, assuming that nitrite concentrations in soil were negligible. Frozen plant and soil samples were sent to an external laboratory (JenaBios GmbH, Jena, Germany) for determining the content of the pharmaceutical indicator substance doxycycline.

2.4 Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were done using the R software (version 4.5.2). Effects of the fertilizer treatment on crop parameters (dry biomass, fresh biomass/marketable yield, total C and N content, CN ratio, and N uptake) were assessed by ANOVA. Model residuals were evaluated visually using quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plots, plots of residuals *versus* fitted values, and residuals *versus* factor levels. If the assumptions of normality and variance homogeneity were not

fulfilled (i.e., if substantial deviation from the diagonal line in Q-Q plots or imbalanced distribution of residuals between fitted values and factor levels was found), the Kruskal–Wallis rank sum test was used instead of ANOVA. Effects of the sampling time (before the experiment, at harvest), the fertilizer treatment, and their interaction on soil parameters (dry matter, pH, total soil C and N content, soil organic carbon, CN ratio, NH_4^+ -N, NO_3^- -N, soil mineral N, soil organic N, and other macro- and micronutrients) were assessed by linear-mixed effects models using the R package “lme4” (version 1.1–38). The sampling time and fertilizer treatment were set as fixed factors, while the plots were set as random factors. Model residuals were evaluated visually using Q-Q plots, plots of residuals versus fitted values, and residuals versus factor levels analogous to as described for ANOVA above. If necessary, a log transformation of dependent variables was applied to meet the assumptions of normality and variance homogeneity. For significant effects, *post hoc* contrast analysis was conducted using the R package “emmeans” (version 2.0.0) and the Holm-Bonferroni method to adjust for multiple comparisons.

3 Results

3.1 Kohlrabi biomass and nitrogen uptake

Kohlrabi dry biomass at the time of harvest - encompassing leaves, bulbs, and roots—was on average 13% lower in the treatment using HEDF compared to the mineral fertilizer treatment (Figure 2A). However, this difference was not statistically significant, indicating that the two treatments had similar effects on biomass production for all parts of the kohlrabi plant. In general, the difference was more pronounced in the bulbs (–17% dry biomass in HEDF) and roots (–19% dry biomass in HEDF) than in the leaves (–7% dry biomass in HEDF) of kohlrabi. Marketable yield, i.e., the fresh biomass of kohlrabi bulbs, was between 54 and 84 t ha⁻¹

(Figure 2B) and reflected the differences in dry biomass with on average 13% lower values in the HEDF treatment compared to the mineral fertilizer treatment (Table 4, see also Supplementary Table S4).

In contrast to biomass, there were significant differences in the total N content of leaves and bulbs between the two treatments (Figure 3A), with on average 29%–30% higher total N content in the HEDF treatment compared to the mineral fertilizer treatment (Table 4). As a result, the overall N uptake was also affected by the treatment (Figure 3B). In leaves, which showed only marginally decreased biomass in the HEDF treatment, the N uptake was significantly higher (+21%) compared to the mineral fertilizer treatment (Table 4). This effect was not found in bulbs, where the N uptake was almost equal between both treatments, whereby the higher total N content compensated for the lower biomass values. Since the total C content was not affected by the treatment (Table 4), the C/N ratio reflected the differences in total N content, with 22%–23% lower values in leaves and bulbs of kohlrabi from the HEDF treatment. Further information on the analyses of plant parameters with values from individual plots can be found in Supplementary Table S4.

3.2 Soil nutrient dynamics

Soil analyses showed no significant treatment effects on Corg content (Figure 4A) and total N content (Figure 4B). Similarly, there were no significant effects on total soil C and soil C/N ratio (Table 5). However, there was a slight tendency to decreased total soil N content (–15% compared to before cultivation) in the mineral fertilizer at the end of the experiment. Furthermore, there were clearly distinct patterns for soil Nmin (Figure 4C). Compared to the sampling before kohlrabi cultivation, soil Nmin significantly increased in both treatments after the cultivation period, yielding on average six-times higher values in the HEDF treatment and 34-

TABLE 4 Average values of plant parameters derived from biomass determination and C/N analysis of kohlrabi leaves, bulb, and roots ($n = 4$); and statistical results from ANOVA (F values) or Kruskal–Wallis tests (χ^2 values).

Plant part	Parameter	Unit	Mineral fertilizer			HEDF			F/χ^2 value ^a ($df = 1$)	Significance
			Mean	±	SD	Mean	±	SD		
Leaves	Total C	g kg ⁻¹ DM	387	±	3	385	±	3	0.8/0.8	n.s.
	Total N	g kg ⁻¹ DM	29.0	±	0.5	37.8	±	1.5	117.4/5.3	$P < 0.05$
	C/N ratio	–	13.3	±	0.3	10.2	±	0.4	165.4/5.3	$P < 0.05$
	Fresh biomass	t ha ⁻¹	39.4	±	4.6	40.9	±	3.8	0.8	n.s.
	Dry biomass	g m ⁻²	480	±	50	446	±	43	1.0	n.s.
	N uptake	kg ha ⁻¹	139	±	13	168	±	11	12.2	$P < 0.05$
Bulbs	Total C	g kg ⁻¹ DM	413	±	3	408	±	8	1.4/0.3	n.s.
	Total N	g kg ⁻¹ DM	21.6	±	0.4	27.8	±	3.3	13.9/5.3	$P < 0.05$
	C/N ratio	–	19.1	±	0.4	14.8	±	1.9	19.4/5.3	$P < 0.05$
	Fresh biomass	t ha ⁻¹	73.9	±	9.5	64.4	±	10.4	1.8	n.s.
	Dry biomass	g m ⁻²	561	±	55	465	±	67	5.0	n.s.
	N uptake	kg ha ⁻¹	121	±	14	130	±	29	0.3	n.s.
Roots	Total C	g kg ⁻¹ DM	361	±	17	357	±	31	0.1/0.1	n.s.
	Total N	g kg ⁻¹ DM	13.9	±	1.8	15.7	±	3.2	1.0/0.3	n.s.
	C/N ratio	–	26.2	±	2.7	23.2	±	3.8	1.7/1.3	n.s.
	Fresh biomass	t ha ⁻¹	4.76	±	0.66	4.43	±	0.32	0.8	n.s.
	Dry biomass	g m ⁻²	95.8	±	12.2	78	±	16.2	3.1	n.s.
	N uptake	kg ha ⁻¹	13.2	±	2.0	12	±	1.1	1.3	n.s.

DM, dry matter; n. s., not significant.

^aKruskal–Wallis tests were done for Total C, Total N, and C/N ratio to determine the level of significance, because analysis of residuals from the ANOVA, models indicated non-linearity (Q-Q plots) and/or heterogeneity of variance (residuals vs. factor levels).

times higher values in the mineral fertilizer treatment (Table 5). This increase was significantly higher for the mineral fertilizer treatment, which had on average five times higher soil N_{min} contents in soil than the HEDF treatment at the end of the experiment. The soil N_{min} in the mineral fertilizer treatment was composed of similar shares of ammonium-N (NH₄-N) and nitrate-N (NO₃-N), whereas soil N_{min} in the HEDF treatment was to 93% in the form of NO₃-N (Table 5). Reflecting the differences in soil N_{min}, soil N_{org} showed a more pronounced tendency for decreased values (–28% compared to before cultivation) in the mineral fertilizer treatment at the end of the experiment (Figure 4D) than total soil N (Figure 4B).

In general, soil pH values showed a tendency to increase from before cultivation to after cultivation by 0.2–0.3, with slightly higher pH values in the HEDF treatment than in the mineral fertilizer treatment (Table 5), reflecting the relatively high pH value of the used FC (Table 2). The analysis of other soil nutrients revealed no significant differences in phosphorus (P), potassium (K), magnesium (Mg), copper (Cu), and manganese (Mn) levels between the two treatments and two sampling times (Table 5). Boron (B) contents in soil showed a tendency to decrease by 22%–24% over time in both treatments, with slightly higher values in the mineral fertilizer treatment compared to the HEDF treatment, which were already present at the beginning of this study due to the pre-trials conducted. Sodium (Na) contents in soil were

significantly increased in the HEDF treatment after the cultivation period by 52% compared to before cultivation, while they were unchanged in the mineral fertilizer treatment (Table 5). Lastly, zinc (Zn) contents in soil decreased after cultivation in both treatments (by 37% for mineral fertilizer and 20% for HEDF) compared to before cultivation, indicating that, irrespective of fertilizer treatment, the plant Zn uptake was higher than the Zn supply from fertilization. Further information on the analyses of soil parameters with values from individual plots can be found in Supplementary Table S5 and Supplementary Table S6. Results from linear mixed-effects models on soil parameters are shown in Table 6.

3.3 Doxycycline as a pharmaceutical indicator

From the screening of 98 pharmaceutical indicator substances, only doxycycline was found in FC (Table 7). The concentration did not notably change between the two analysis dates (Supplementary Table S7), indicating that no further degradation of doxycycline took place during the storage period. In the kohlrabi bulb samples and soil samples from all HEDF treatments, no quantifiable concentrations of doxycycline were found (values below the limit of quantitation).

4 Discussion

As hypothesized, the applied combination of FC and NUF resulted in comparable biomass growth and marketable yield of kohlrabi as conventional mineral fertilizer. This lines up with previous studies using similar HEDF combinations for growing maize (Boness et al., 2024) and okra (Sangare et al., 2015). The slightly lower yield in the HEDF treatment could have been due to initial N immobilization caused by the additional organic matter introduced by FC (Geisseler et al., 2021). However, there was no detectable change in soil Corg content in the present study, which can be attributed to the relatively short duration of the experiment. Increases in soil Corg generally occur over longer time scales and may require repeated applications before statistically significant differences become apparent (Diacono and Montemurro, 2010). In addition, it has to be noted that the systematic design utilized in this study may not have taken into account confounding effects from unknown gradients in the greenhouse and the that the statistical power is limited by the small number of replicates (n = 4). While the former could have been avoided by randomization of plots, it is a common practice in greenhouse trials to use systematic approaches to address known gradients in microclimate within the greenhouse such as differences in the light regime (Brien et al., 2013).

Despite this, there were potential differences in plant growth dynamics between the HEDF and mineral fertilizer treatments, which were particularly visible in the increased plant N content and N uptake in the HEDF treatment at the end of the experiment. One explanation for that could be the nutrient imbalance between the treatments, as fertilizer application was adjusted plant N demand, while differences occurred in P, K, and micronutrient

contents applied. Higher P and K amounts applied to soil in the HEDF treatment (Supplementary Table S2) could have enhanced nitrogen uptake, e.g., by stimulating microbial N transformation through higher P supply (Xia et al., 2023) or K⁺ ions facilitating root NO₃⁻ absorption and transport to shoots (Cao et al., 2025). Another explanation is that the fertilizer application technique could have affected plant growth and N uptake dynamics, as not all NUF was applied at the beginning of the cultivation period, but also at later stages. In addition, re-mineralization of N from FC might have provided additional N for plant uptake during the later stage of the experiment. Similar observations have been reported by Saliu et al. (2023), who found initially slower growth of maize and tomato plants with nutrients from human urine recovered on gastropod shells, which was later compensated by faster growth rates compared to conventional mineral fertilizer. Consequently, we speculate that a combination of the different factors discussed above was responsible for the higher plant N uptake observed in the HEDF treatment compared to the mineral fertilizer treatment. Irrespective of this, the higher N contents in bulbs and leaves of kohlrabi from the HEDF treatment at the end of the experiment suggest that the used combination of FC and NUF was suitable for providing kohlrabi plants with N. A direct connection between leaf N content and photosynthetic activity is well-known for C3 plants (Evans, 1989). Therefore, the higher plant N uptake in kohlrabi leaves from the HEDF treatment was likely associated with a higher photosynthetic activity at the end of the experiment, which possibly could have leveled out the observed slightly lower biomass gains at a later harvest date.

The most notable differences between the mineral fertilizer and HEDF treatments were found in soil N pools at the end of the

experiment. The increased N_{min} contents in the mineral fertilizer treatment may have resulted from continued nutrient release from coated fertilizer granules combined with lower plant N uptake efficiency relative to HEDF treatments. In addition, the reduction in soil N_{org} suggests that part of the plant N uptake and residual soil N_{min} may have originated from net mineralization of soil organic matter (SOM). Based on average values across the four mineral fertilizer plots, total plant N uptake (274 kg N/ha) exceeded the total fertilizer N input (221 kg N/ha), while soil N_{min} increased by 152 kg N/ha. This corresponded to an apparent reduction in soil N_{org} of 346 kg N/ha (Supplementary Table S8). In contrast, soil N_{org} in the HEDF treatment increased by 65 kg N/ha, which is in line with findings of Boness et al. (2024), who found an increase of total soil N after growing maize in a pot experiment with FC. Mineral N fertilization has previously been associated with enhanced short-term N mineralization from SOM (Chen et al.,

2014; Xu et al., 2023), although long-term studies often report reduced SOM decomposition rates (Zang et al., 2016). One possible explanation for the observed decline in soil N_{org} in the mineral fertilizer treatment is that greater plant growth increases rhizosphere C inputs and stimulates microbial N mineralization from SOM (Bernard et al., 2022). However, this mechanism was not directly measured in the present study and should therefore be interpreted cautiously.

The interpretation of the N balance is further limited by uncertainties associated with soil heterogeneity, bulk density estimates, plant biomass sampling, and analytical variability in soil and plant N measurements. Small cumulative errors in these components may substantially influence calculated N surpluses or deficits. In particular, overestimation of N uptake in the plant biomass or underestimation of soil N_{org} could partly explain the apparent magnitude of N depletion from SOM in the mineral

TABLE 5 Average values of general soil parameters and nutrient contents before and after kohlrabi cultivation ($n = 4$).

Parameter	Unit	Before cultivation						After cultivation					
		Mineral fertilizer			HEDF			Mineral fertilizer			HEDF		
		Mean	±	SD	Mean	±	SD	Mean	±	SD	Mean	±	SD
Dry matter	%	90.4	±	0.3 ^b	90.0	±	0.8 ^b	89.6	±	0.6 ^a	88.9	±	1.5 ^a
pH	–	7.3	±	0.4 ^a	7.6	±	0.1 ^{ab}	7.6	±	0.1 ^{ab}	7.8	±	0.1 ^b
Total C	t ha ⁻¹	15.3	±	1.3	14.5	±	0.4	13.6	±	1.3	15.6	±	1.4
Total N	t ha ⁻¹	1.27	±	0.20	1.18	±	0.03	1.08	±	0.06	1.27	±	0.11
C/N ratio	–	12.2	±	1.1	12.3	±	0.5	12.6	±	0.6	12.3	±	0.3
Corg	t ha ⁻¹	14.5	±	1.5	13.1	±	1.2	14.5	±	2.1	13.7	±	1.2
NH ₄ -N	kg ha ⁻¹	1.5	±	3.0 ^a	0.0	±	0.0 ^a	84.5	±	65.7 ^b	2.3	±	1.8 ^a
NO ₃ -N	kg ha ⁻¹	3.1	±	1.4 ^a	4.8	±	1.6 ^a	71.7	±	45.0 ^c	27.0	±	4.9 ^b
Nmin	kg ha ⁻¹	4.6	±	4.4 ^a	4.8	±	1.6 ^a	156.1	±	106.3 ^c	29.3	±	6.0 ^b
Norg	t ha ⁻¹	1.27	±	0.20 ^b	1.17	±	0.03 ^b	0.92	±	0.11 ^a	1.24	±	0.10 ^b
P	mg 100g ⁻¹ FM	16.5	±	1.7	14.4	±	1.8	13.6	±	2.7	13.7	±	2.4
K	mg 100g ⁻¹ FM	6.7	±	3.0	4.0	±	1.1	4.1	±	2.9	2.7	±	0.3
Mg	mg 100g ⁻¹ FM	3.8	±	1.1	2.7	±	0.1	3.2	±	0.4	2.9	±	0.1
B	mg kg ⁻¹ FM	0.37	±	0.06 ^b	0.28	±	0.02 ^{ab}	0.29	±	0.08 ^{ab}	0.24	±	0.01 ^a
Cu	mg kg ⁻¹ FM	6.6	±	1.8	4.7	±	0.2	4.8	±	0.3	5.0	±	0.6
Mn	mg kg ⁻¹ FM	72	±	24	50	±	4	63	±	4	61	±	7
Na	mg kg ⁻¹ FM	16	±	3 ^a	21	±	4 ^a	21	±	4 ^a	32	±	2 ^b
Zn	mg kg ⁻¹ FM	14.6	±	3.8 ^b	12.2	±	1.2 ^b	9.2	±	0.3 ^a	9.8	±	2.0 ^a

^a–^cLetters indicate significant effects of sampling time, fertilizer treatment, and their interaction derived from *post hoc* tests on linear-mixed effects models ($\alpha = 0.05$); FM, fresh matter.

fertilizer treatment. For example, if the found $\pm 10\%$ – 20% uncertainty (SD) in plant N uptake and soil Norg estimates is considered, the calculated apparent soil Norg depletion in the mineral fertilizer treatment could in reality be substantially reduced. Furthermore, residual mineralization effects from the FC applied during the preceding pre-trial likely contributed to the N dynamics observed in the HEDF treatment (Supplementary Table S8). Nevertheless, despite these uncertainties, the contrasting trends between treatments were consistent across replicate plots: mineral fertilizer treatments showed higher residual soil Nmin and lower soil Norg, whereas HEDF treatments showed lower Nmin accumulation and maintenance or increases in Norg. This pattern suggests that HEDF application promoted more gradual N release and greater short-term N immobilization associated with FC-derived organic matter inputs.

A higher availability of Nmin in soil after the cultivation can lead to increased N leaching and nitrous oxide emissions (Di and Cameron, 2002; Butterbach-Bahl et al., 2013). In the HEDF treatment, two circumstances could have led to the lower Nmin contents in soil at the end of the experiment. First, the immobilization of excess Nmin was likely increased through the FC application. It is well known that C-rich soil amendments like compost can reduce N leaching and N emissions by increasing N

retention capacity, primarily through the immobilization of inorganic nitrogen into organic forms (Amlinger et al., 2003; Diacono and Montemurro, 2010). Albeit this might be related to delayed N losses due to later N re-mineralization (Sørensen et al., 1994; Geisseler et al., 2021). Second, the application of NUF over time, which was done to avoid potential adverse effects from high sodium concentrations, could also have contributed to avoiding excess Nmin in soil by only providing as much Nmin as plants can take up. Although a similar functionality was provided by the coating of the slow-release mineral fertilizer used as a comparison in this study.

Overall, this suggests that while recycling fertilizers may not adversely affect kohlrabi biomass growth compared to mineral fertilizers, the lower availability of Nmin in the recycling fertilizer treatment (N immobilized by organic matter from FC) could potentially limit nutrient uptake and growth in other contexts. On the other hand, the reduced availability of Nmin in soil could prevent N leaching and make more N available for plant growth in the following crop. Unfortunately, it was not possible to collect enough leachate from the greenhouse trial to analyze potential differences between the fertilizer treatments. This was possibly due to slow infiltration rates and blockages in the technical system of the lysimeter greenhouse plots.

TABLE 6 Results of linear mixed-effects models on soil parameters and nutrient contents before and after kohlrabi cultivation. The models included sampling date (Date) and fertilizer treatment (Fertilizer) as fixed effects and the plots as random intercepts.

Parameter	χ^2 value (<i>df</i> = 1)			Significance		
	Date	Fertilizer	Date × fertilizer	Date	Fertilizer	Date × fertilizer
Dry matter	8.66	1.28	0.31	<i>P</i> < 0.01	n.s.	n.s.
pH	4.29	5.36	0.51	<i>P</i> < 0.05	<i>P</i> < 0.05	n.s.
Total C	0.25	0.83	6.72	n.s.	n.s.	<i>P</i> < 0.01
Total N	0.73	0.84	6.90	n.s.	n.s.	<i>P</i> < 0.01
C/N ratio	0.46	0.06	0.48	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Corg	0.16	2.29	0.21	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
NH ₄ -N	10.19	8.59	10.61	<i>P</i> < 0.01	<i>P</i> < 0.01	<i>P</i> < 0.01
NO ₃ -N	30.71	0.54	11.06	<i>P</i> < 0.001	n.s.	<i>P</i> < 0.001
Nmin	23.29	2.62	11.27	<i>P</i> < 0.001	n.s.	<i>P</i> < 0.001
Norg	2.85	2.06	10.27	n.s.	n.s.	<i>P</i> < 0.01
P	3.87	0.67	2.21	<i>P</i> < 0.05	n.s.	n.s.
K	3.54	3.57	0.50	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Mg	0.56	5.00	2.36	n.s.	<i>P</i> < 0.05	n.s.
B	4.73	5.79	0.71	<i>P</i> < 0.05	<i>P</i> < 0.05	n.s.
Cu	1.69	2.50	5.06	n.s.	n.s.	<i>P</i> < 0.05
Mn	0.01	3.13	3.43	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Na	9.70	11.23	3.96	<i>P</i> < 0.01	<i>P</i> < 0.001	<i>P</i> < 0.05
Zn	11.02	0.33	2.08	<i>P</i> < 0.001	n.s.	n.s.

n.s., not significant.

TABLE 7 Average of doxycycline concentrations found in two samples from the applied fecal compost and in soil and kohlrabi samples taken at the end of the experiment.

Sample	Doxycycline concentration			Unit	Replicates
	Mean	±	SD		
Fecal compost	11.5	±	0.7	µg/kg DM	<i>n</i> = 2
Soil	<1	±	–	µg/kg DM	<i>n</i> = 4
Kohlrabi bulbs	<1	±	–	µg/kg FM	<i>n</i> = 4

DM, dry matter; FM, fresh matter.

Salt stress from high sodium contents in NUF is a potential problem for crop cultivation, as indicated by the increased sodium contents in the soil of HEDF plots at the end of the experiment. Although this increase was still moderate, repeated NUF application could contribute to increased salinity of soils in the long term. According to Abrol et al. (1988), soil salinity problems generally become critical at electrical conductivity values exceeding 4 dS m⁻¹ or under conditions promoting sodicity, which can negatively affect soil structure, infiltration capacity, and nutrient availability. Because soil salinity and sodicity were not considered as initial objectives of the present study, soil electrical conductivity and sodium adsorption ratio were not measured. However, the observed increase in soil Na concentrations highlights the importance of monitoring salinity-

related parameters during repeated HEDF applications. For example, Sangare et al. (2015) found in a pot experiment lower okra yield when using human urine as sole fertilizer and attributed this to increased soil salinity. Contrarily, a long-term field trial with human urine in Denmark over 20 years showed no adverse effects on barley growth and a sodium adsorption ratio that was well-below the threshold for sodic soils (Hansen et al., 2026). It has also been suggested that the combined application of NUF with another carbon-rich amendment such as compost (including FC) can help to alleviate soil salinity (Häfner et al., 2023). In the present study, no visible salt stress symptoms, such as chlorosis, wilting, or growth reduction, were observed in the kohlrabi plants during the experiment. *Brassica* spp. generally able to tolerate moderate salt

stress due to various underlying physiological mechanisms (Shahzad et al., 2021). In addition, the soil sodium concentration of 32 mg kg⁻¹ (ppm), fell within the range of 5–40 ppm, which is considered normal for agricultural soils (University of Delaware, 2026). Ultimately, to facilitate the use of HEDF, a reduction of salt consumption in human nutrition would be needed, as also suggested by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2012). This would directly decrease sodium concentrations in human urine and would therefore also help to mitigate increased soil salinity from NUF application.

Micropollutants such as pharmaceutical residues are a major concern regarding the safety of HEDF (Winker, 2009; Varju, 2025). So far, there is little knowledge on the fate of pharmaceutical substances entering the soil through fertilizer application. Data from long-term studies using wastewater irrigation or sewage sludge application on agricultural soils show that certain poorly degradable pharmaceutical residues such as carbamazepine and diclofenac can accumulate in soils and can be transported to leachate water over time (Kinney et al., 2006; Ternes et al., 2007). In the present study, we looked at the fate of doxycycline, which was found as the only indicator substance from the screening of 98 pharmaceutical residues in the used FC. That does not mean it was the only pharmaceutical substance from the screening that was present, but the only one above the limit of quantitation, which for some substances was even higher than the found concentration of doxycycline (Supplementary Table S3). Furthermore, other pharmaceutical substances that were not included in the screening could have been present, further limiting the interpretability of results found in this study. In general, it is also possible that low input concentrations of pharmaceutical substances (below detection limit) accumulate in soil after repeated application of HEDF, increasing the risk of plant contaminant uptake. In the case of this study, it was not possible to retrieve doxycycline in quantifiable amounts in the kohlrabi bulbs and the top soil at the end of the experiment, which we attribute to the dilution from the incorporation of FC into soil. This is in-line with a previous study showing very low pharmaceutical uptake of white cabbage fertilized with FC and NUF (Häfner et al., 2023), and a recent model-based assessment indicating low health risks of pharmaceutical accumulation in crops irrigated with wastewater (Nightingale et al., 2025). Furthermore, in a Swiss pilot project, it has been shown that pharmaceutical concentrations in FC were around 30times lower compared to digested sewage sludge (Schinkel et al., 2025), underpinning the low risk of pharmaceutical residues in FC. Nevertheless, long-term experiments are needed to study if pharmaceutical residues from repeated HEDF application can accumulate in soil over time or are leached out into groundwater. Although many pharmaceutical residues can be degraded by microbial activity (Kummerer, 2009), some substances like tetracyclines (including doxycycline) are more stable in the environment (Hamscher et al., 2002) and can cause problems for soil health or the spread of antibiotic resistances (Thiele-Bruhn, 2003).

5 Conclusion

In general, the results of this study show that HEDF are suitable for growing kohlrabi plants with similar performance compared to state-of-the-art mineral compound fertilizer. Beyond demonstrating

comparable crop yields, this study provides additional insight into the effects of HEDF application, particularly on N dynamics in the plant-soil system under controlled greenhouse conditions. Based on this, we recommend that fine-tuning of the application of NUF should be done to provide plants with N at the time when they need it the most. Nevertheless, the approach taken to distribute the NUF application over time potentially also reduces the negative effects of high sodium concentrations in soil, which were found as a potential HEDF-related trade-off in this study. Further studies are needed to fully optimize the timing and rate of NUF application to reduce risks from high sodium contents and maximize N use efficiency. In particular, long-term monitoring of salinity-related parameters will be important to assess whether repeated HEDF application may contribute to soil sodicity or salinity under intensive cultivation systems. Pharmaceutical residues in HEDF and particularly in FC seem to be of lower concern, but this assessment is only based on the limited information gathered from one indicator substance in this study (i.e., doxycycline), and more information is needed from long-term experiments to determine the risk of accumulation for environmentally stable pharmaceutical residues. More research is also needed to determine how the repeated application of FC affects soil organic carbon and N cycling, in particular nitrate leaching. The lower soil N_{min} concentrations observed in the HEDF treatment in this study suggest a more gradual N release and altered short-term soil N cycling. Ultimately, the combined application of NUF and FC might be promising not only to provide plants with a wider spectrum of nutrients but also to increase long-term soil health by adding additional organic material from FC to the soil and thereby prevent soil degradation. By using kohlrabi as a short-cycle vegetable crop intended for direct human consumption, this study contributes relevant insights into the applicability and safety of HEDF in intensive horticultural production systems, as well as the evidence base needed for scaling up HEDF-based circular nutrient flows whilst safeguarding food safety and environmental integrity.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Material, further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Author contributions

CG: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. SK: Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that generative AI was used in the creation of this manuscript. We used ChatGPT to create a graphical abstract (attached as supplementary image) and Gemini

3 to identify and summarize relevant literature. A description of AI use is included in the Acknowledgements section.

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Supplementary material

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2026.1856888/full#supplementary-material>

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